

Deliverable 1.1.4.1

PLATFORM REQUIREMENTS ANALYSIS

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D1.1.4.1 Platform requirements analysis

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General Information

Summary

This deliverable presents the findings of a requirements analysis focused on the stakeholder group of energy researchers for the NFDI4Energy platform. The primary objective of this empirical study was to identify the needs and challenges faced by energy researchers from various disciplines in their daily work. Based on these findings, a list of potential services that could address these needs within the future NFDI4Energy platform was derived. This work builds upon prior research by Werth et al. [1], which proposed a concept for an “Open Digital Platform for Interdisciplinary Energy Research and Practice”. Our study extends their work by offering detailed insights specific to energy researchers and reflecting critically on the key services previously identified.

The study used a snowball sampling approach, ensuring a diverse range of participants in terms of age, position, research perspective, and discipline (see sample overview in the appendix). A total of fourteen semi-structured expert interviews (15 interviewees, including one two-person interview) were carried out between December 2023 and April 2024. The interviews, held both online and in person, were conducted in German and lasted 60 to 90 minutes each. Prior to the interviews, participants completed a pre-interview questionnaire, providing additional context and aiding in the selection process. For data analysis, the team employed a group-based qualitative content analysis approach, utilizing Maxqda24 (24.5.1) software, with both deductive and inductive coding applied. Quotes have been translated from German to English for this deliverable (the published dataset will remain available only in German). Changes in speakers during quotations are indicated with 'I' for the interviewer and 'R' for the interviewee. Overall, the analysis identified 13 major needs and challenges, summarized in tables within the deliverable, with further supporting data included in the appendix.

Deliverable within NFDI4Energy

The analysis yielded actionable insights to inform the development of the NFDI4Energy platform, emphasizing practical solutions to address the identified needs of energy researchers. The 13 major needs derived from the interviews highlight hurdles related to research data management and interdisciplinary collaboration, among other challenges. Based on the interviewees’ feedback and supplementary input from the authors, a set of potential services for the NFDI4Energy platform was proposed. These include tools for streamlined research data management, enhanced support for interdisciplinary collaboration, and resources tailored to the unique workflows of energy researchers.

All interview guidelines and the anonymized dataset will be published under restricted access in the eLabour data repository (<http://elabour.de/>) to ensure transparency and reproducibility. These materials are intended to support further research and refinement of the proposed services. The findings of this deliverable are summarized in tables and will be further elaborated upon in a forthcoming paper [2], expanding on the methodological and thematic contributions of this analysis. This work complements the requirements analysis of industry partners (D3.1.3.2), reinforcing the comprehensive approach of NFDI4Energy to meet the diverse needs of its stakeholders.

Related deliverables: D2.1.1.1, D3.1.3.2, D6.3.6.1

Deliverable: Overview of research needs, challenges and relevant services for the NFDI4Energy platform

The tables below summarize the key findings derived from qualitative expert interviews conducted with fifteen energy researchers from diverse disciplinary backgrounds (see sample overview on p. 25). The transcribed interviews were analyzed by using qualitative content analytical procedures utilizing the software Maxqda24 (24.5.1). Each table is structured as follows:

- **Perspective:** The broad disciplinary background of the interview partners who mentioned the need.
- **Mentions:** The number of interviews in which the identified need was addressed.
- **Description:** A summary of the specific issues encountered by energy researchers.
- **Suggested Services:** Proposed solutions or tools to address these needs, as suggested by interview partners and/or the authors.
- **Exemplary Quotes:** Selected verbatim remarks from interviewees, offering direct insights into the challenges and expectations.

Need 1: Addressing and contacting research participants	
Perspective (interview)	Social Sciences & Humanities (EI01, EI14), Economics (EI02)
Mentions	3/15
Description of related challenge	First, for researchers with a local or regional focus (e.g., conducting local case studies), the selection of case regions and the establishment of contact with potential research participants is a time-consuming step in the research process. Second, due to topical trends, there is a risk of over-researching certain regions, which may lead to a decreased willingness of local actors to cooperate with scientists (see also Need 3).
Exemplary quote challenge	"Also, what is a bit tedious is really reaching out to potential interview partners." (EI01: 24)
Suggested service	Register for potential research participants or stakeholders: People who declare their willingness to participate in research projects or who could act as stakeholders can be added to a register without having to have a profile on the platform. Relevant data for researchers can be entered in the register (e.g. on which topics and in which region they can make statements, what function they have in the context of energy, ...) as well as contact details. Researchers who are registered on the platform can thus easily contact them directly via the platform. The aim is to reduce the frustrating search for research participants and stakeholders, which is good for both researchers and target persons.
Exemplary quote service	<p>"[...] but that would be pretty cool if you had the overview to know, who has actually done research on topic xy in [area]? Or in the predecessor project? Who has conducted interviews there? [...] maybe to have the opportunity to see the results or just call people and ask, how did that go for you?" (EI01: 24)</p> <p>"Who is actually working on the topics? [...] it would be cool if I could say at a glance okay, who is doing research in Germany right now from a social science perspective on, let's say, citizen energy empowerment, energy transition or whatever, and then I could see, ah yes, these 15 other people have also tackled this, who could click through at a glance. [...] Can they help me, for example, when it comes to finding cool stakeholders?" (EI01: 32)</p>

Need 2: Enhance science communication	
Perspective (interview)	Social Sciences & Humanities (EI01, EI03), Technical (EI03, EI09, EI11)
Mentions	4/15
Description of related challenge	It is challenging for researchers to prepare their scientific findings for non-scientists. This includes reaching out to specific target groups (e.g. the public or politicians) and demonstrating the everyday relevance of their findings.
Exemplary quote challenge	<p>"[...] but I have also encountered this in previous projects, where people then say, 'yes, but I already talked to so-and-so last year and nothing really came out of it.' So, that is a point that also affects science as a whole, where I often think we should perhaps communicate better: What is politics? What is science? What happens with the results and how does it work? [...] I have often encountered that people were a bit frustrated that they have to tell the same things to someone else again. Which we can also understand from their perspective" (EI01: 24)</p> <p>"So science communication plays a role in relation to politics. Mainly for me at European level, but it is certainly just as important at national level. It plays a role in relation to the public. We need to professionalize this (...) because it plays a very important role in this whole discussion that the public is well informed. The whole transformation of the energy system that we are facing will cause us the greatest problems if we fight against half-truths in public." (EI11: 61)</p>
Suggested service	Science Communication Hub: Section on the platform that helps researchers effectively communicate their findings to policymakers, industry leaders, and the general public. The hub offers tutorials and advice, templates for targeted outreach and policy briefs, as well as news and updates on outreach opportunities and events in the energy research community, to increase the impact and relevance of research findings.
Exemplary quote service	/

Need 3: Documentation of empirical research, overview of current and past research projects and researchers	
Perspective (interview)	Social Sciences & Humanities (EI01, EI03, EI14), Technical (EI03)
Mentions	3/15
Description of related challenge	It is challenging for researchers to find out which topics have already been researched in which regions and using which methods. It is also difficult to obtain low-threshold information on participating institutions, contact persons and contact options for research projects.
Exemplary quote challenge	<p>"In other words, to really look at the topic, to see who can do it, who is currently researching it, what projects are there at the moment? Which I can also find out by doing a Google search, but not so quickly. And who is doing it in the regions where I am researching" (EI01: 84)</p> <p>"And it is also easier for me to know what similar research has already been conducted, what can ultimately be built upon, and how the research can be made accessible" (EI03: 21)</p> <p>"It would be good to consider how to somehow aggregate this, so that one knows, ah yes, this project for example or, or this institute was interviewed in this context before, the interview covered this and that topic, and maybe one could therefore get back in touch with the corresponding researchers to find out, well, to establish more of a connection through, through the researchers rather than constantly bothering the interviewed people." (EI14: 24)</p>
Suggested service	Interactive geographical map: The service provides a comprehensive overview of researchers, their research interests, current and past research projects, regional focus, research discipline, methods, publications and datasets. It enables direct contact with researchers and provides instant access to shared data and publications. The aim is to provide a quick overview of the research landscape and facilitate seamless communication and collaboration.
Exemplary quote service	"That's another question, of course, because a platform like this also offers an overview, has an active map where you can see in which regions, for example, data has been recorded and then you can click on it and see, there have already been research projects in [area]." (EI03: 33)

Need 4: Enhance findability of scientific data	
Perspective (interview)	Social Sciences & Humanities (EI01, EI03, EI15), Technical (EI03, EI11, EI12), Economics (EI05, EI06&07, EI08, EI15), Environmental (EI15)
Mentions	8/15
Description of related challenge	It is a challenge for researchers to obtain data in general and in sufficient depth. This data has to be collected from different sources. Access to data is also made more difficult by the fact that it is restricted, for example because only certain groups of people have access, it is behind payment barriers or is not publicly available at all. Access to transnational data is difficult. Foreign languages also make access complicated. In addition, existing databases are cluttered. The lack of availability of data is a decisive factor in research taking place.
Exemplary quote challenge	<p>"Well, and what's also a bit annoying is not having access. But I think this is a general problem in the scientific community, that you don't have access to some papers. It's frustrating because you actually need them to place your research in context." (EI01: 24)</p> <p>"So the biggest difficulty, depending on the region and things, can actually be extremely difficult to find data. So that can actually be an extremely big difficulty [...] But yes, data is often one of the biggest problems." (EI08: 23)</p>
Suggested service	Federated search: Provides a unified platform to access and link diverse research artifacts from the field of energy research. This includes datasets, publications, models, methodologies, and other research outputs. By integrating multiple repositories, the platform enables users to conduct advanced searches with filtering options based on criteria such as region, topic, energy source, and research methodology. Additionally, the platform can provide links to international databases, ensuring comprehensive access to global energy research. The primary aim is to facilitate the discovery of high-quality data, foster cross-project collaboration, and streamline access to primary sources.
Exemplary quote service	"Ultimately, it would be extremely helpful to have a meta-platform that provides you with the sub-sources for all relevant points. In some cases, it is actually helpful if you can find secondary data, especially in the literature. You usually have a lot of trouble finding out if I find a value in the literature, but it doesn't fit, then finding out the primary source. That is actually helpful. I think it would really help to have a kind of automatic chaining of metadata etc., so to speak. Because it's often helpful to get the data in the most detailed form you can. Because then you can always aggregate and process it yourself. That's always relatively easy. It's difficult when other people have already touched the data and have somehow processed it themselves. Because then it's difficult to process them again, so to speak. In other words, it would be great to have the opportunity to access primary data in some way. And then, of course, it would be ideal to always know for each data set which assumptions have somehow been included in the calculation, i.e. if it is not primary data." (EI08: 29)

Need 5: Successful communication and collaboration in inter- and transdisciplinary contexts	
Perspective (interview)	Social Sciences & Humanities (EI03), Technical (EI03, EI04, EI09, EI11, EI12), Natural Sciences (EI16)
Mentions	6/15
Description of related challenge	In inter- and transdisciplinary contexts, researchers face the challenge of communicating clearly with researchers from other disciplines (and possibly non-researchers, e.g. stakeholders). Possibilities include developing a common vocabulary or having “translators” at the interfaces. This also includes being able to anticipate and abstract the required scope of knowledge from one's own discipline for other disciplines, both in terms of content and methodological aspects, an open-mindedness.
Exemplary quote challenge	<p>"[...] how difficult it is to understand this language, i.e. to understand what the other side needs to know. [...] So to understand what they actually need to know. To think about what they actually need to know, to abstract, to say, this part of the knowledge is irrelevant for them, but this part, you have to tell them now, otherwise they can't work with it. It's like thinking for myself what I have to tell them or people like you and then understanding what they tell me." (EI04: 19)</p> <p>"To understand their methods, i.e. to develop respect for how their methods work and to say, Ah great, it's clear that research is also a good thing [...]" (EI04: 21)</p>
Suggested service	Inter- and Transdisciplinary Academy: Online tutorials with real-world case studies, simulations, and role-playing exercises aimed at improving communication across disciplines and stakeholders. The service would also provide best practice examples, experience reports (e.g. [3]), and guiding questions to foster better understanding between disciplines regarding research topics and methods. Researchers would benefit from curated lists of interdisciplinary journals, tools to navigate different research phases and their pitfalls, and conflict resolution strategies. Additionally, a dedicated forum would allow researchers to share tips, resources, and experiences.
Exemplary quote service	/

Need 6: Find, network and exchange with researchers	
Perspective (interview)	Social Sciences & Humanities (EI01, EI14), Economics (EI05) Technical (EI11), Natural Sciences (EI16)
Mentions	5/15
Description of related challenge	Despite the growing recognition of the importance of interdisciplinary research, many researchers face challenges in establishing and maintaining meaningful connections with colleagues from other disciplines. While there are some existing platforms and initiatives that facilitate interdisciplinary exchange, they may not be widely known or utilized, and may not be tailored to the specific needs of different research communities. Furthermore, institutional and systemic barriers, such as lack of funding, time, and resources, can hinder the ability of researchers to engage in interdisciplinary collaboration. To address these challenges, there is a need for more targeted and inclusive exchange formats, as well as digital forums that can facilitate the sharing of ideas and expertise across disciplines.
Exemplary quote challenge	<p>"And of course it would also be cool to have a lawyer to write to who is familiar with the subject. [...] And it would have been cool to just talk about it with an engineer who can really classify it technically in a completely different way than I can. And of course I can read it. I do that too, because I want to be able to talk to my interview partners on an equal footing. But it would also be really cool to be able to ask them questions. And conversely, I was recently at a project office in Berlin and talked to them about citizen participation and they found it really exciting." (EI01: 84)</p> <p>"Perhaps the most likely problem is to familiarize young scientists, who may not come from such strongly networked chairs, with this community and to introduce them to it. That might be the first steps into this community. That is perhaps something that could be consciously supported." (EI11: 39)</p> <p>"[...] I believe that in these technical disciplines, deep professional networking is much more important than interdisciplinary networking." (EI11: 29)</p>
Suggested service	<p>Networking Section: Enables researchers to connect with each other, share knowledge, and collaborate on research projects, including...</p> <p>a) Researcher Profiling and Directory: Feature that allows researchers to create profiles showcasing their disciplines, key research topics, and expertise, and connect with potential collaborators. Hence, a searchable database of researchers is established, organized by discipline and current research projects, enabling a targeted search and both disciplinary and interdisciplinary networking. Additionally, a Research Partner Matching feature can be used to find suitable partners for research projects.</p> <p>b) Profiles for Internal Project Groups: These profiles can also be used to form internal project groups and can be added to project structures (e.g. Task Areas) to provide an overview of the knowledge and expertise within the project. This service meets a need that bigger consortia have in general and may incentives them to initially use the platform.</p>

	<p>c) Moderated Forum: Forum for a moderated exchange between researchers (from different disciplines). The section can be used to ask questions and provide aggregated information from experts on various topics, allowing users to quickly get up to speed on new areas of research.</p>
Exemplary quote service	<p>"It would be helpful to have a platform where you can find aggregated information from experts on the various topics that are relevant in the field, which you can either pass on or use yourself to read up on things that you are not necessarily working on yourself. A fund beyond what Wikipedia offers would be helpful under certain circumstances." (E11: 63)</p> <p>"So it always has a certain purpose or I approach it with an expectation. In other words, with LinkedIn, I don't really use it at all, because you get flooded with information there. And this is much, much more specific, with a real expectation of networking in a targeted way." (E16: 63)</p>

Need 7: Context information on existing data	
Perspective (interview)	Social Sciences & Humanities (EI01), Economics (EI08, EI10) Technical (EI09, EI11), Natural Sciences (EI16)
Mentions	6/15
Description of related challenge	It is challenging for researchers to have sufficient context for existing data. It is unclear where data comes from, how it was generated and which contextual factors played a role (e.g. goal and relevance of the research project, preliminary assumptions, survey period, data collection process, sampling, information on participants, input data used, comparative data used, uncertainties in data, corrections (due to technical reasons) of changed data). This challenge is associated with the obstacle of finding the primary source of data.
Exemplary quote challenge	<p>"So first of all, of course, I would need information about the circumstances under which this was originally raised. [...] Simply to understand, what was the aim of the research project? How were the interviewees selected? (...) Yes, and then exactly as you say. So, a brief contextualization so that I simply know, not in the sense of who exactly is this? But in the thinking of the original project that dealt with this, why were they relevant?" (EI01: 38)</p> <p>"[...] we have taken apart a data center. (.) [Name] was also involved and wanted to replicate this in the life cycle assessment. And [name] uses this [database] and saw that this is standard electronic waste. So it's not computer waste, but a hairdryer, a toaster and all sorts of things. Exactly, and that's a mix and we should use this mix for our data centers. And then we said, no, that's not possible." (EI09: 35)</p>
Suggested service	Metadata standard: Establish a metadata standard that includes comprehensive contextual information such as project goals, data collection methods, sampling strategies, and preprocessing steps. When primary data is used to aggregate a dataset, it must be clearly and transparently disclosed. The metadata schema must also be applicable to various research artifacts, as different types of data, such as qualitative data (e.g., interview transcripts), may require specific contextual information for reuse. Metadata should be machine-readable, with automated validation ensuring completeness and reusability. The goal is to create transparency and enable researchers to confidently assess and use existing data.
Exemplary quote service	"If it [the platform] actually provide the processes behind this data generation, make them transparent, use any scripts, Jupyter, Dotbox or whatever. I would find it very helpful if they could provide this directly, so that in case of doubt you can understand how the data is generated and reproduce or adapt it if necessary. I could also imagine that it would be really interesting, particularly with regard to relevant scenario calculations, if the underlying input data from, let's say, at least large and important energy system analyses or scenarios were actually available in some kind of structural form - I would find that very helpful." (EI10: 79)

Need 8: Reputation for shared data sets	
Perspective (interview)	Social Sciences & Humanities (EI01), Economics (EI02) Technical (EI09, EI11)
Mentions	3/15
Description of related challenge	Researchers feel that they receive too little reputation for uploading data, especially when measured in relation to the effort required to process the data accordingly. At the same time, there are different ideas about how reputation can look (e.g. being named as a co-author when using the data, naming the researchers (and not just naming the project), citing the dataset).
Exemplary quote challenge	I: "But you didn't get a reward for uploading it, did you?" //R: "Nope." (..)// R: "I think somewhere in the datasets it says that they are from our research project, but then it says the research project and not the name. (...) Yes, it would be nice to leave your footprints." (EI09: 44-45)
Suggested service	<p>To enhance recognition for sharing datasets several features can be used:</p> <p>Researcher Attribution System: Ensure proper recognition by attributing the dataset to the researcher(s) rather than just the research project. This could include prominent author-level citations when the dataset is reused.</p> <p>DOI Assignment for Datasets: Automatically assign Digital Object Identifiers (DOIs) to uploaded datasets, making them citable in publications and easily traceable.</p> <p>Co-authorship License: Provide an optional co-authorship license where researchers who significantly contribute data can be included as co-authors on related publications, if reused.</p> <p>Dataset Impact Visualization: Offer visualization tools (e.g. download counts, citation metrics) to show researchers how often their data has been accessed or cited. This could motivate researchers by showing the reach and impact of their data.</p> <p>User Feedback and Interaction Tool: Allow users to provide feedback or engage with the data owners directly through the platform. This interaction could facilitate collaboration and data improvement.</p> <p>Data Preparation Acknowledgment Badge: Badge system that acknowledges the effort involved in preparing and sharing high-quality data. This could be displayed on researcher profiles, signaling their contribution to open science and data sharing.</p> <p>Usage Probability Estimator: Feature that estimates the potential reuse or demand for a dataset based on its content, metadata quality, and the needs of the community. This gives researchers an idea of how valuable their data might be.</p>

**Exemplary quote
service**

"Quite often, I think you also have the feeling that, well, okay, you don't know how many users would really want to use it. If I now knew more concretely, okay, the 30 municipal utilities would use the tool or the information as soon as it was uploaded, I would perhaps do it sooner, because we also have an intrinsic motivation or could then also advertise by being able to explicitly say, I know that 30 other project partners have also implemented it afterwards. Or if I know how much it will bring, if I can estimate how much it will bring later." (E102: 87)

"And that doesn't immediately result in co-authorship, but it does provide a source citation option, which is great for many people when they see, oh, I've created a dataset here and it's being used so often, then it seems to be an important dataset." (E116: 55)

Need 9: Time-saving and uncomplicated data processing	
Perspective (interview)	Social Sciences & Humanities (EI14), Economics (EI02, EI06, EI07, EI08, EI10) Technical (EI09)
Mentions	7/15
Description of related challenge	For researchers, preparing their own data for use by others is challenging for a number of reasons. First, it is perceived as extra work, time-consuming and does not necessarily bring benefits to the researchers themselves. Secondly, comprehensible documentation as a step in data processing is not implemented organically in the work process. This process also requires researchers to know what information must be available in prepared data. Thirdly, data processing sometimes means not just a single effort, but maintenance over time. That is why data processing is often not undertaken and therefore no data is uploaded.
Exemplary quote challenge	"So, giving data, or if we now have companies that say, yes, you can do something with our data, (.) put that in. But how do you put it in there so that it's also useful for others? I think that's still a lot of work." (EI09: 55)
Suggested service	<p>To streamline data processing and save time, the following services can be implemented:</p> <p>Multi-Format Data Upload: Support a wide variety of data formats, accommodating different types of research artifacts commonly used across disciplines. The platform should handle not only quantitative datasets but also text-based and visual data, ensuring broad compatibility.</p> <p>Automated Data Conversion Tools: Provide built-in tools for automatic conversion between common data formats and transformation across widely-used data standards (e.g. converting between SPINE and OEP formats). These tools reduce the workload for researchers by simplifying data preparation.</p> <p>Data Transformation Scripts: Offer a library of pre-built scripts (e.g. Python, R) for routine tasks such as data transformation, cleaning, and reformatting. Researchers should also be able to upload and share their own scripts, fostering collaboration and reuse within the research community.</p> <p>Qualitative Data Tools: Provide information on existing tools that facilitate the processing of qualitative data. This could include AI-based transcription tools (e.g. ATrain, noScribe), as well as anonymization tools (e.g. QualiAnon) for handling personal or sensitive data. Simple instructions should also be available to ensure compliance with GDPR and other legal frameworks, helping researchers legally redact or transform sensitive data.</p> <p>Metadata Generator: Implement automated metadata generation tools that update metadata following data conversion or transformation. This ensures that the essential context is preserved, regardless of the data format, making datasets more findable and reusable. Additionally, the tool could identify relevant data from associated publications, enhancing dataset discoverability.</p>

**Exemplary quote
service**

"So let's put it this way, there are now quite a few artificial intelligence tools that do the transcribing for you, that completely knocks all the language into you, understands it very well. [...] In other words, you don't have this super elaborate "dot dot dot, pause, swallow". Yes, but of course you already have the content somehow. And if you actually go in from an expert interview perspective and not from a narrative perspective, then that's actually enough, in my opinion. And if it's that easy, then I'll do it, then I'd do it." (EI05: 30)

"What you can do in any case is to provide examples of existing scripts, some of which you can then perhaps adapt for your own purposes. [...] And above all, there are a few established data formats that exist. So there's the OEP format, there's the IMC data format. There is some kind of data format from the Spine people. If you had at least some standard conversions between these data formats, that would actually be pretty cool." (EI08: 63)

Need 10: Increase usability of existing data	
Perspective (interview)	Social Sciences & Humanities (EI14), Economics (EI02, EI06, EI07, EI08, EI10) Technical (EI09, EI12)
Mentions	8/15
Description of related challenge	For researchers, compiling and processing data from others for their own use is challenging for several reasons. Firstly, existing data sets lack data points that are relevant for their own research. Secondly, the scope of the existing data does not completely match their own. Thirdly, the data format must be adapted for their own research. Fourthly, data from several data sources, each with different data formats, must be combined with each other, which can lead to the above-mentioned challenges. Overall, data processing can be vulnerable to errors. Automated data processing is almost impossible due to the diversity of topics.
Exemplary quote challenge	<p>R: "I think that's because we just have a problem, so we don't have a, here's a database and do something with it. Instead, we have to somehow work everything out on foot. [...] Because it's not, do Matlab and then take database XYZ."</p> <p>I: "Exactly, take the CSV out and enter."</p> <p>R: "Exactly. We work a lot with CSV data, but we usually get it from the industry and then have to process it for ourselves." (EI09: 63-65)</p>
Suggested service	<p>Automated Data Integration Tools: Metadata-driven search feature that can intelligently recommend related datasets based on their content and structure and suggest possible links between them. This would help connect tables (e.g. linking a dataset with CSV outputs from one source with another database) by identifying key relationships. Also helpful to provide suggestions for mixed methods approaches, indicating datasets that combine qualitative and quantitative data effectively.</p> <p>Aggregation Suggestions: Clearly indicate on the platform which datasets can be combined or used to aggregate new datasets, based on shared variables, methodologies, or data formats. This functionality would point out the compatibility of datasets for different research purposes.</p> <p>Linkage Visualizations: Offer a visual tool that graphically maps out the connections between datasets, enabling users to see how various data tables and sources are interrelated. This can make it easier for researchers to identify relevant data and understand the relationships between different datasets, reducing the time spent on manual investigation.</p>

**Exemplary quote
service**

"Most of the time, or at least in my experience, the most exciting results are actually only obtained when you link several different pieces of data together. In other words, perhaps for this platform that you want to offer, one added value would be to offer this data at all, the other added value would be the whole thing, or if that is somehow possible, to suggest links between this data. If you think of relational databases, then you have table A, table B and they can be linked to each other via some key relationship." (E106&07: 56)

Need 11: Comprehensive knowledge about data management	
Perspective (interview)	Social Sciences & Humanities (EI03, EI14), Economics (EI02, EI06, EI07) Technical (EI03, EI04, EI12)
Mentions	7/15
Description of related challenge	Researchers are faced with the challenge of a lack of (basic) knowledge about research data management (e.g. filing data, storing data, data protection, administrative issues when uploading data). Improper data storage and documentation can lead to errors during data processing and steps in data processing can no longer be traced. In addition, unclear documentation makes it more challenging to process the data for publication.
Exemplary quote challenge	"I don't think it's a secret that when you prepare interviews like this, you do them, conduct them and evaluate them. Of course, you always have to generate a lot of data, including where to store what, how to secure it and how to save it. And then you always need content from each interviewee. Then they don't answer straight away. You have to remind them again. So, of course, there are a lot of processes that are very time-consuming, and I don't know if you've done it a few times, but you know you have to plan the appropriate time." (EI03: 21)
Suggested service	Educational programs and guidelines: Provide guidelines and templates for various topics that set certain standard (e.g. DMP). Offer formats for knowledge transfer on data management (e.g. courses, short input videos). The aim is to ensure uniformly high quality in the area of data management, which is relevant for researchers, but also ensures quality on the platform and is therefore also important for platform users.
Exemplary quote service	I: "And what kind of training would help you? Could that somehow be a service that could be on a platform, in the form of a template on how such a plan could be structured, a best-practice video or what would you wish for? Let's say you've found a great project advertisement that you really want to apply for with your team. But it says you have to submit a data management plan." R: "So what now? Yes, then perhaps a how-to-explainer example for the field here, energy system analysis, would be a few examples or a bit of a guide on what you need to do. That would certainly be useful." (EI10: 67-68)

Need 12: Comprehensive knowledge about legal aspects for sharing data	
Perspective (interview)	Social Sciences & Humanities (EI01, EI03), Economics (EI02, EI05, EI06, EI07) Technical (EI03)
Mentions	6/15
Description of related challenge	<p>Researchers are faced with the challenge that they often have uncertainties regarding legal aspects of data management and publication. There is a lack of knowledge and foresight regarding the naming of subsequent disclosure of data in the context of declarations of consent. In this context, data management after the end of the project or in the event of staff changes is also considered critically. Particularly in the case of qualitative interview data, the challenge is to anonymize the data and still provide sufficient context, coupled with the fear of possible identification if this data is published. Additionally, there is also legal uncertainty regarding the publication of secondary data.</p>
Exemplary quote challenge	<p>"I've also had the situation myself where someone would have liked to work with data that I once collected, but that would have been difficult under data protection law, because you actually have to know that at the time the data is collected and then you have to obtain consent for it to be passed on, even if only in anonymized form. And I didn't do that at the time. And exactly with the person from whom I would have liked to have the data or where it would have been cool to be able to use it, which was also the case that it was simply legally impossible." (EI01: 26)</p> <p>"And perhaps one last point, these data records that we then generate, we also combine them with data from various other sources, which we may also request, where we have to say exactly, for this and this use, I need the data, then I get the data. And then, with our data, our data set is created, to what extent we are authorized to use this data, even if the raw data or the data that we have received from other sources, even in aggregated form or something like that, has been processed in there, whether we are authorized. So there are also legal issues where you tend to say, I'd rather not give out the data, not that there are any problems with a third party who has provided me with parts of the data." (EI06&07: 109)</p>
Suggested service	<p>Legal Compliance Tool: Develop a legal compliance tool that guides researchers through the legal aspects of data sharing. This tool could provide a checklist to help ensure all necessary steps for compliance with GDPR and other relevant data protection regulations are completed, including obtaining informed consent, anonymizing data, and managing data retention.</p> <p>Legal Section in Education Programs and Guidelines: Create a centralized legal knowledge hub where researchers can access up-to-date information about data protection laws or templates for defining usage terms (see Qualiservice), ethical considerations, and best practices for data sharing. This hub would include legal guidelines, case studies, FAQs, and contacts for expert legal advice. Provide information that helps researchers evaluate the legality of reusing existing datasets, especially when combining them with data from other sources.</p> <p>Licensing and Data Usage Guidance: Provide standardized data licensing options (e.g., Creative Commons, Open Data Commons) and guidance on</p>

	selecting the appropriate license for different datasets. This service would also offer templates for defining clear usage terms, so researchers know what is permitted when sharing or reusing data.
Exemplary quote service	/

Need 13: Ensured quality management for uploaded data	
Perspective (interview)	Economics [EI10], Natural Sciences (EI16)
Mentions	2/15
Description of related challenge	Researchers face the challenge of having to be able to recognize the quality of uploaded data. This applies to both raw data (e.g. by sorting out measurement errors) and processed data (e.g. describing changes that have been made).
Exemplary quote challenge	"We don't just put all the data in there, otherwise you have good and bad data and incorrect data. [...] And with the raw data, you have to sort out measurement errors so that no one, who perhaps doesn't have the insight, suddenly models with a measurement error afterwards. " (EI16: 37)
Suggested service	<p>Data Quality Assessment and Certification: Implement an automated data quality assessment system that checks datasets for completeness, consistency, and accuracy, providing feedback to the person uploading the data. The platform could assign a quality certification badge (e.g., "Verified," "Partially Verified," "Unverified") based on the outcomes of these checks. This would allow researchers to quickly assess the quality and reliability of uploaded data.</p> <p>Error Flagging and Commenting System: Introduce an interactive error flagging feature where users can report suspected issues or inconsistencies in datasets. Other researchers and data providers can respond to these flags by confirming or explaining potential discrepancies. This system fosters collaboration and improves dataset accuracy over time.</p> <p>Quality Reviewer: Assign quality reviewers or platform curators who can provide expert oversight on the data uploaded. These reviewers could respond to flagged data, investigate data anomalies, and work with data owners to resolve issues. This would create an added layer of trust for users who rely on the platform's data.</p>
Exemplary quote service	<p>"And then an admin, if there was someone who responded to questions, comments or hints, i.e. if someone said that there seemed to be something inconsistent in the data, if they responded to this, perhaps they would make it visible to others, that would of course also be helpful. That would give me the feeling that it is quality-checked." (EI10: 87)</p> <p>"What we also have is that we have different data categories. Firstly, according to data age, then uncertainties that can occur during the measurement. So we have very reliable data, less reliable data and uncertain data. So we also have different data categories. And it is then important for the scientists to be able to treat the different data differently when weighting them." (EI16: 39)</p>

Overview of Suggested Services

Suggested Service	Need	Mentions
Federated search	4	8/15
Increase usability of existing data	10	8/15
Educational Training on RDM	11	7/15
Time-saving Data Processing	9	7/15
Inter- and Transdisciplinary Academy	5	6/15
Features for Legal Compliance	12	6/15
Metadata Standard	7	6/15
Networking Section	6	5/15
Scientific Communication Hub	2	4/15
Interactive Geographical Map	3	3/15
Open Science Recognition Features	8	3/15
Register for potential research participants or stakeholders	1	3/15
Data Quality Management	13	2/15

Sample overview

Total number of interviewees (n): 15

Figure 1 Sample overview (age, position, discipline, orientation)

All relevant quotes

Need 1: Addressing and contacting research participants

"Also, what is a bit tedious is really reaching out to potential interview partners." (EI01: 24) [challenge]

"But that would be pretty cool if you had the overview to know, hey, who has actually done research on community energy in [area]? Or in the predecessor project? Who has conducted interviews there? I don't know, just to know about the protests against a new power line or something like that, hey, there was something there before and maybe to have the opportunity to see the results or just call people and ask, hey, how did that go for you? So just not to put so much strain on people." (EI01: 24) [service]

"Who is actually researching these topics at the moment? Researching and who is in the research regions, so my research is often location-based, it's not like that everywhere, but it would be cool if I could say at a glance, okay, who is doing research in Germany right now from a social science perspective on, let's say, citizen energy, empowerment, or energy transition, whatever, and then see, Ah yes, these 15 other people have also tackled this, who could click through at a glance. [...] And if I were to say, who is doing research in [area] right now? There are a lot of people there. [area], exactly the same topic, to see what they are actually doing? Do I perhaps already know them? Can they help me, for example, when it comes to finding cool stakeholders? [...] And if it were possible to access qualitative data that has been collected elsewhere or simply project reports on certain topics in a central location or region. Of course, that would also be cool if you didn't always have to search for everything. So that would definitely save me work. I don't know if I would have the time to analyze a lot of qualitative data from other people, but I could well imagine reading the summary or simply descriptive reports. So short summaries of what they found out." (EI01: 32) [service]

"But when you think about qual[itative research], how laborious it sometimes is to find interview partners and, depending on the topic you're researching, how much trust you have to build up and what you have to talk to them about, then you drive there and spend ages on the phone with them. 'And no, we really don't work for the nuclear lobby' or whatever." (EI01: 72) [challenge]

"That's why I find it most difficult to collect data in the qualitative area with the interview partners. Where we have a good network, that's where we get [something] or that's where it fits. I see that with my students. If they have to do something as part of their Master's degree, they can't find enough interview partners." (EI02: 46) [challenge]

"And as I said, getting to the person you want to reach. Maybe that's just another point and in that sense it's certainly helpful and I've already heard that from various people, that there is of course a certain or that there is a danger that there can be a certain interview fatigue or simply a fatigue more or less in the broad community to always be available for researchers, in quotes, to fill out surveys, to do interviews, because, as I said, we are not the first ones." (EI14: 24) [challenge]

Need 2: Enhance/ enable science communication towards the public and politics

"[...] but I have also encountered this in previous projects, where people then say, 'yes, but I already talked to so-and-so last year and nothing really came out of it.' So, that is a point that also affects science as a whole, where I often think we should perhaps communicate better: What is politics? What is science? What happens with the results and how does it work? [...] I have often encountered that people were a bit frustrated that they have to tell the same things to someone else again. Which we can also understand from their perspective" (EI01: 24) [challenge]

I: "And the last point again, I just mentioned it briefly in the area of transparency, science communication, if you think about it on this platform. For example, which target groups would be particularly relevant for your research? Where would you say there is perhaps the most interest in your research, but where is there perhaps also the greatest need to further inform certain groups? And can you perhaps also think of specific formats that the platform should serve? "

R: " (...) Yes, well, I deal a lot with forms of engagement and of course everyone who is somehow confronted with it will either promote it or, if we want to read protest as engagement, deal with it. So I think there are many actors on the ground, i.e. municipalities, people and communities. So there are civil society actors working there, as well as economic development actors, depending on the signs. So if the aim is to somehow advance the energy transition on the ground, then this can also have positive economic effects. so it's more about the local regional level and practical actors. I notice that they are very interested in what I am currently researching. So they often say, let's stay in touch after the interview. That's actually very nice and a lot of people ask what else is happening? Yes, that's what I would say. But that also means that the formats, because of course these are people who are very involved with a lot of things and don't have the technical energy know-how that someone has who only deals with it, that this should simply be prepared, that there are perhaps handouts of a few pages of guidelines on how to make an energy cooperative, for example, or a comparison of the legal form of community energy and then just with a view to framework conditions, but also with a view to technical possibilities and limits and things like that. So I think that would be well received. [...] And for science communication to the outside world, I think it's generally important to always consider the practical benefits. So I'm a fan of the ivory tower. I think science is free and should be able to do whatever crazy things it can think of. But I think in terms of good science communication, it's great to be able to emphasize that. Why is this exciting right now? Why is this innovative right now? What can we take away from it? What questions are there or could there be in the future? Very practically in everyday life, which we can tackle with it." (EI01: 101-102) [challenge]

"I mean, of course, the question is always there, even in the public debate now. I mean, there's a disenchantment, a lot of things aren't working out the way they should. People are very unsure, what's going to happen here? Then people still think, Ah, 100% renewables is not even possible. Where I think to myself, oh no, we still haven't managed to somehow prepare this in such a way

that people there, that they believe that there is a common social understanding or consensus that this is the way and that it is also possible to achieve an energy transition alone." (EI03: 33) [challenge]

"So what I don't think other platforms are able to do is create this link to industry, to politics. I think that could be something that is somehow more interesting, that you can then also say how you can then perhaps also somehow bundle results and then also make them available in a way for various decision-makers, so to speak." (EI03: 61) [challenge]

" [...] I think we also have a bit of a task to educate people. Guys, it's all connected." (EI09: 9) [challenge]

"So science communication plays a very big role, I think. I do that when it comes to CO2 transport, the things that I'm now doing more in terms of (...) science policy. You can also find some things on the internet where I'm present. So science communication plays a role in relation to politics. Mainly for me at European level, but it's certainly just as important at national level. It plays a role vis-à-vis the public. We have to (...) professionalize that, because it plays a very big role in this whole discussion that the public is well informed. The whole energy system transformation that lies ahead of us will cause us the biggest problems if we fight against half-truths in public." (EI11: 61) [challenge]

Need 3: Documentation of empirical research, overview of current and past research projects and researchers

"but that would be pretty cool if you had the overview to know Hey, who has actually carried out research into community energy in the [area]? Or in the predecessor project? Who has conducted interviews there? I don't know about the protests there against a new power line or something like that, just to know Hey, there was something there before and maybe to have the opportunity to see the results or just call people and ask Hey, how did that go for you? So just not to put so much strain on people." (EI01: 24) [challenge] [service]

"Who is actually researching these topics at the moment? Researching and who is doing it in the research regions, so my research is often location-based, it's not like that everywhere, but it would be cool if I could say at a glance, okay, who is doing research in Germany right now from a social science perspective on, let's say, citizen energy empowerment, energy transition or energy transition, whatever, and then see, Ah yes, these 15 other people have also tackled this, who could click through at a glance. [...] And if I would say, who is doing research in [area] right now? There are a lot of people there. [area], exactly the same topic, to see what they are actually doing? Do I perhaps already know them? Can they help me, for example, when it comes to finding cool stakeholders? [...] And if it were possible to access qualitative data that was collected elsewhere or simply project reports on certain topics in a central location or region, that would of course also be cool if you didn't always have to search for everything. So that would definitely save me work. I don't know if I would have the time to analyze a lot of qualitative data from other people, but I could well imagine reading the summary or simply descriptive reports. So short summaries of what they found out. And if it were possible to access qualitative data that was collected elsewhere or simply project reports on certain topics in a central location or region, that would of course also be cool if you didn't always have to search for everything. So that would definitely save me work. I don't know if I would have the time to analyze a lot of qualitative data from other people, but I could well imagine reading the summary or simply descriptive reports. So short summaries of what they found out." (EI01: 32) [challenge] [service]

I: "What would be the most important services that come to mind for you? Do you have any application examples?"

R: "Yes, yes, definitely. In other words, to really look at the topic, to see who can do it, who is currently researching it, what projects are there at the moment? Which I can also find out by doing

a Google search, but not so quickly. And who is doing it in the regions where I am researching" (EI01: 83-84) [challenge] [service]

"And it is also easier for me to know what similar research has already been conducted, what can ultimately be built upon, and how the research can be made accessible" (EI03: 21) [challenge]

"That's another question, of course, because such a platform also provides an overview, of course, and has an active map where you can see in which regions, for example, data has been recorded and then you can click on it and see what I know. There have already been research projects in [area]." (EI03: 33) [service]

"But of course it would be helpful to have a better overview. What research has already been done, and who are the contacts?" (EI03: 33) [challenge]

"As I said, one contact person would be enough in my opinion to be able to write to someone again." (EI03: 33) [challenge]

"actually the topic, who has already collected certain data on various topics?" (14: 22) [challenge]

"I don't want to say that, well, we don't want to reinvent the wheel, but we do to a certain extent, because you just don't know who all in Germany has actually already, (...) drilled into the subject in depth." (14: 22) [challenge]

"It would be good to consider how to somehow aggregate this, so that one knows, ah yes, this project for example or, or this institute was interviewed in this context before, the interview covered this and that topic, and maybe one could therefore get back in touch with the corresponding researchers to find out, well, to establish more of a connection through, through the researchers rather than constantly bothering the interviewed people." (EI14: 24) [challenge]

"In other words, there is a large database that summarizes these projects and also the operating companies, but we then had to do some additional research to collect the contact details." (EI14: 26) [challenge]

"that it can be ensured that this data is not stored in the individual institutes in drawers, in virtual or digital drawers, but that it can be ensured that one knows, oh yes, this institute has, so that one can perhaps use a keyword search to access certain information, who works with what and what data was collected?" (EI14: 30) [challenge]

Need 4: Enhance access to scientific data

"Well, and what's also a bit annoying is not having access. But I think this is a general problem in the scientific community, that you don't have access to some papers. It's frustrating because you actually need them to place your research in context." (EI01: 24) [challenge]

"But that would be pretty cool if you had the overview to know, hey, who has actually done research on community energy in [area]? Or in the predecessor project? Who has conducted interviews there? I don't know about the protests there, a new power line or something, just to know, hey, there was something there before and maybe to have the opportunity to see the results or just call people and ask, hey, how did that go for you? So just not to put so much strain on people." (EI01: 24) [service]

"And if it were possible to access qualitative data that was collected elsewhere or simply project reports on certain topics in a central location or region, that would of course also be cool if you didn't always have to search for everything. So that would definitely save me work. I don't know if I would have the time to analyze a lot of qualitative data from other people, but I could well

imagine reading the summary or simply descriptive reports. So short summaries of what they found out." (EI01: 32) [challenge] [service]

"There are already some approaches that do not make transcripts completely freely accessible, of course, but that they are subject to certain access restrictions, i.e. explicitly qualitative research data centers have already created such approaches so that, for example, as a registered researcher you can also get access to less anonymized versions of the transcripts" (EI03: 28) [service]

"But then I also have some problems, even within my own former institute. I worked at the [institute] for a while, which is in [location], and I sometimes had problems, even with my own colleagues, because I wanted data sets and then they were on this nice platform and then it was somehow difficult to actually get hold of the raw data. Sounds a bit strange now, but it was actually like that." (EI03: 40) [challenge]

"I usually find that the repositories are quite confusing, even in the statistical area. So it's very difficult to see where the journals are submitting what and then to see who is doing what, which authors are doing it and so on." (EI05:32) [challenge]

I: "I'm just wondering how you decide which problems to pursue and which not?"

R: "Actually, partly according to the availability of data." (EI06&07: 35-36) [challenge]

"Originally due to this urban logistics project, I had done a lot of research into problems in the field of urban logistics. However, the availability of data is traditionally very poor because you have to rely on data from the operator and you can't get hold of that. [Organization] doesn't give out any data, for example. With others, when it comes to [type] service providers, it's also not so easy to obtain data and accordingly these were problems that you may have encountered in this area, but which you can't address on the data side and accordingly this is then not pursued further. On the other hand, we had then identified that you can access the data via an interface from operators, a topic or perhaps also an area that we, I hadn't even had on our radar before and because data was then available there" (EI06&07: 37) [challenge] [service]

I: "So it really is the crucial problem for starting a new project? (...)"

R1: "Well, when I think back to our conversations, it's often like that, yes."

I: "Conversations that you both had with each other?"

R1: "Yes, or with colleagues in the context of the doctorate, when it comes to (.) you have a certain pressure to publish, what can you publish, then a decisive factor is often, is there any data at all? So when I think back to my publication, our publication, that was always a decisive factor."

R2: "Or am I able to collect this data myself with reasonable effort?"

R1: "Yes, exactly."

I: "Reasonable in terms of time and effort?"

R2: "Time and effort, exactly."

R1: "Yes, and technical possibilities."

R2: "And availability. Exactly. There are primary sources for a wide variety of data, which are completely distributed, which of course, or mostly do not have the format that I would need to (..) answer my research question." (EI06&07: 38-47) [challenge]

"In other words, perhaps intended for this platform that you want to offer, one added value would be to offer this data at all, the other added value would be to suggest the whole thing, or if that is somehow possible, to suggest links between this data. If you think of relational databases, then you have table A, table B and they can be linked to each other via some key relationship. So I don't know, I then have data for a particular zip code, the number of inhabitants, for example. That's my one data source that I offer on the platform. On the other hand, I have (...) wind turbines per zip code. And then that you can automatically link this table, these two tables or data via the zip code with each other and that the scientist is relieved of this in a certain form. That would definitely offer added value in terms of simply saving time. Because, as I said, this particular added value

often lies in linking several pieces of information to form an overall picture." (EI06&07: 56) [service]

"In other words, the higher or the finer the level of aggregation of the data, the more difficult it usually is to obtain it or to get hold of it somehow, and that was often the kind of problem we tended to have. It wasn't that data wasn't available for a certain question, but that it wasn't sufficiently granular." (EI06&07: 58) [challenge]

R1: "The data set that [name] mentioned is actually not publicly accessible for the time being. So only on request and with a signature on the privacy policy."

R2: "And only for certain groups."

R1: "Exactly. So as a university institution, you have access to it, otherwise not." (EI06&07: 61-63) [challenge]

"So the really exciting data sets are either not available or behind paywalls" (EI06&07: 103) [challenge]

"So this functionality I mentioned is available at Statista, where you can, no, not Statista, is that the Statista site? Destatis, Destatis, exactly. Where you can also click together the table yourself. (.) Exactly, the idea would be that I need a certain basic data set in order to answer my, so I have a specific question where I really need the data in any case, but then it might be suggested to me that this and that data could be linked to it via this and that column. And maybe it's just the functionality of the first one that gives you the idea, okay, that would be interesting to take a look at, because I could use it to answer this and that question." (EI06&07: 139) [service]

"So the biggest difficulty, depending on the region and things, can actually be extremely difficult to find data. So that can actually be an extremely big difficulty [...] But yes, data is often one of the biggest problems." (EI08: 23) [challenge]

"Ultimately, it would be extremely helpful to have a meta-platform that provides you with the sub-sources for all relevant points. In some cases, it is actually helpful if you can find secondary data, especially in the literature. (.) It's usually quite difficult to find out if I find a value in the literature, but it doesn't fit, then to find out the primary source. That is actually helpful. I think it would really help to have a kind of automatic linking of metadata and so on. Because it's often helpful to get the data in the most detailed form that you can. Because then you can always aggregate and process it yourself. That's always relatively easy. It's difficult when other people have already touched the data and have somehow processed it themselves. Because then it's difficult to process them again. (.) In other words, it would be great to have the opportunity to access primary data in some way. (.) And then, of course, it would be ideal to always know for each data set which assumptions have somehow been included in the calculation, i.e. if it is not primary data." (EI08: 29) [service]

"What is more difficult is access to secondary data." (EI11: 23) [challenge]

"I think our focus at the moment is a little further away from the specific energy data because it is not publicly available." (EI12: 15) [challenge]

"I think there is simply little accessible data" (EI12: 17) [challenge]

"But what I would like to see, for example, before you mention it, is accessibility to texts and legal texts, including literature and case law from other legal systems. So I am also a passionate comparative lawyer. I always like to look at how things work abroad. And if you at least had links to databases in other countries, I could imagine that would be helpful. So with the procurement of foreign publications, that also starts with European law. We always look at the German literature, but European law is written about in all member states. And that is actually more difficult for us to access, unless it has been published in English or French in leading journals." (EI15: 49) [challenge]

"We are networked and have our databases and so on. But what would be a good tool, for example, as I said earlier, a linking tool, right? Links to energy law, if I'm speaking in disciplinary terms now, I have to, that's my primary concern and that's the only thing I've learned in the beginning, so a linking tool with references to databases, especially in other European countries or perhaps at European level and also in non-EU countries, where you could find out more about energy law, about energy legislation. That's the first thing that comes to mind." (EI15: 69) [service]

"First of all, I think it is important for such a platform, i.e. this open energy platform, to collect, as you say, which specialist information systems or databases already exist for individual disciplines, let's say. So, if someone is interested in biomass, they have to find what is already available. And if someone is interested in a [specific field], they might find a link to the specialist information system, [specific field], which we have. We also have a second specialist information system called Geophysics. And that's how it's structured for us, that the specialist information system Geophysics really contains, let's say, the specialist information itself in data rows and columns." (EI16: 37) [service]

"I see added value in all of them in any case, but where I find a very strong link to NFDI for Earth or to our geothermal topic, which, as I said, could almost be at home with both, is definitely the registry." (EI16: 57) [service]

Need 5: Successful communication and understanding in interdisciplinary and transdisciplinary contexts

"I can say from everyday life, just to come back to interdisciplinary research, it's a lot of work. Especially when people are not, let's say, interdisciplinary, but rather come from different disciplines. It's a lot about first developing a common language, a common understanding of the system. What are we even talking about here? And then you also need the openness of the relevant researchers to say okay, I'm going to think outside the box and see what the other discipline could provide me with as added value, so to speak." (EI03: 17) [challenge]

"But it's just really difficult. Yes, this language, that's what I notice again and again when I interact with [name] or with the researchers, with [name], with the researchers from this field, how difficult it is to understand this language, i.e. to understand what the other side needs to know. So not that I'm spouting some kind of technical Latin all the time, which is of no use to them. So to understand what they actually need to know. To think about what they actually need to know, to abstract, to say, this part of the knowledge is irrelevant for them, but this part, you have to tell them now, otherwise they can't work with it. It's like thinking for myself what I have to tell them or people like you and then understanding what they tell me." (EI04: 19) [challenge]

"Yes, so simply, what do I have to tell them and how can I understand what they do and also and I think there is another exciting dimension to this process. (...) Understanding their methods, developing respect for how their methods work and saying, Ah great, it's clear that research, you know, as an engineer I always say only what you can measure and build and calculate and so on, that's research, but also understanding that there are many other methodological approaches and so on, so I think that's also a hurdle that you have to overcome and that I've been able to overcome in the last few years, so to speak. [...] And you just have to make sure that these people who manage the interface are effective, so that they can then spread the word in their communities and sensitize them and say Now is the right moment, now I need you. Yes, my disciplinary researchers, now I need to come here to the interface, do you need to talk to them? It's enough if there are a few more translators." (EI04: 21) [challenge]

"I've already clashed with a few chemists who said, it's your job to recycle it. I said, but I'm telling you now, if you do it like this, it won't work. I can't do magic." (EI09: 15) [challenge]

I: "Are you the bridge between all these stakeholders?"

R: "Yes, I would say I know both sides. That's sometimes an advantage. (...) You often have to talk differently when you're out and about with other people." (EI09: 22-23) [challenge]

"But as soon as you arrive with a different profile, then it becomes, ah, can they do this or that? (...) Because they all understood each other, of course, because they were given the same vocabulary etc..But you can't see the wood for the trees. In your own swamp, you were kind of like, where did I come from, doing research, then you did everything really well, patting each other on the back and stuff like that. But as soon as someone from the outside came in, and that was usually me, (...) I always intervened and asked why like this and why not like that? And that can also be totally misunderstood. For me, a resource is something completely different than for a computer scientist, for example. And I always experience that with my projects. As soon as you start working in an interdisciplinary way, you need a vocabulary. So when you do something like that, always with an explanation, what does that mean? Because everyone, depending on the situation, and now you don't just have to start from university, now you also have to start from people who have never attended a university, which is not a bad thing. But I would say that an electrician in training is taught completely different concepts than we are here at university. And then you have to consider that electricians are very different from computer scientists. People always say that they all understand each other.(.) So for me, the first half, the first six months of the project, was all about vocabulary. So sometimes we made an extra Excel list of what means what, in what context." (EI09: 25) [challenge]

"However, I have also seen that this interdisciplinarity, I would say, actually reaches its limits somewhere in disciplinary research. Because the things that we actually do in thermodynamics, and I can say that we do them very successfully, would not really be understood by other colleagues. In lectures, I mean, you've heard these lectures too, I can only ever talk about them at a very high altitude. There are limits to interdisciplinarity and there really are limits, I think." (EI11: 17) [challenge]

"I try, so if it's just me talking to people from the other department, then I already know the (.) words that I have to use so that the other person understands me, whether I'm talking about super resolution or downscaling, for example. But most of the time I try to abstract it. And to start from the goals and so on. What do we want? And to use as few technical terms, technical jargon as possible at first and then, once you're on the same page, then, okay, we'll call it X, we'll do Y and then you'll (...) come to a relatively good agreement at some point." (EI12: 11) [challenge]

"when I work with groups that have completely different definitions of terms, that have their own technical language and you constantly have to go back and forth as a translator. So among the geosciences, which are all geoscientists, they all have their own language. Even if, of course, they also say, yes, it's interdisciplinary, one person does it. No, for me geosciences are a large group. But when I work with our programmers alone, with IT people who do front-end and back-end programming, they have no idea about geosciences or natural sciences at all, but they have to somehow link this data, which will be visualized later, together well, bring it together and write programs for it. This means that geoscientists and IT specialists have to talk to each other and produce a joint result. And it's exactly the same when we process data, we want economists to understand it so that they can then say whether geotomy is actually economically viable in this location or not. In other words, we have to break down our very complex findings to the essentials and describe them in a way that economists can understand. And for me, this actually means in an interdisciplinary way that I summarize the essentials from my specialist area and also ask the other specialist area to tell me the essentials and describe them to me in a way that I can understand, because I'm a layperson." (EI16: 29) [challenge]

"Communication is the be-all and end-all. And again, the will to communicate, (.) I also observe that in my own colleagues here in the geosciences.(.) They are obviously not at all, either they are not willing or they really can't do it. There are also people who can't abstract. They stay in their little pond, so to speak. They can't get out of it. I've noticed that too. Sometimes they don't have the ability, but quite often they don't really want to." (EI16: 31) [challenge]

Need 6: Find, network and exchange with researchers

"And from my perspective, I think it's great when I can talk about it with people who are more familiar with energy market design than I am, or with political scientists who have analyzed policy frameworks for energy policy, for example, because I'm not involved in the details and also with engineers and technicians who can explain things in a completely different way: how does it actually work and what is actually possible? And I realized that in an essay I once wrote on local heating, it was really valuable that I had a colleague with whom I am also friends. He's an engineer who works at [name] and knows so much about heat and grids that I was able to ask him, what have I got in mind here? Is that even realistic? Is it even feasible?" (EI01: 18) [challenge]

I: "What would be the most important services that come to mind for you? Do you have any application examples?"

R: "Yes, yes, definitely. So to really look at the topic, to see who can do it, who is currently researching it, what projects are there at the moment? Which I can also find out through a Google search, but not so quickly. And who is doing it in the regions where I am researching and what I also find really exciting is who knows about technical issues that I come across in my research? So if now, or also on legal issues, for example, if yesterday an interviewee said yes, there's also a new Citizens' Energy Act coming among us, I'll have to look it up again. so and there it would of course be totally, so I have to do it myself now, I have to inform myself, read it up again. I mean, I know that there are new packages coming and all that, but what exactly is in them and all that. And of course it would also be cool to have a lawyer to write to who is familiar with the subject. And you're also interested in my research. Maybe because she's been working on the topic for too long. And to say you can just give an assessment. [...] And it would have been cool to just talk about it with an engineer who can really classify it technically in a completely different way than I can. And of course I can read it. I do that too, because I want to be able to talk to my interview partners on an equal footing. But it would also be really cool to be able to ask them questions. And conversely, I was recently at a project office in Berlin and talked to them about citizen participation and they found it really exciting. Just to hear from my research about the reasons for participating and the reasons for being against it." (EI01: 83-84) [challenge] [service]

"I mean for modeling, for example, they also have this open modeling platform, where you can see which modelers are out and about, which teams there are, and I think that's kind of cool. And especially when you're talking about how you can bring technical or engineering people and social scientists closer together? Of course, I think it's a really, really good idea to know what the social sciences are like. What is the overview there? What is the current state of affairs? Because I think it's actually a bit more difficult to get an overview than it might be with energy modeling, for example. I think it's probably easier to find information somehow. So that's why I also like the idea of using matchmaking to say okay, these are more the people who are working on the work" (EI03: 53) [service]

"I always thought to myself, why am I doing this right now? Why am I working my way through regulatory documents when there are apparently people at the Commission who are drafting these documents or network operators who are drafting these things and I'm struggling to understand them at all. And what I actually noticed, interestingly enough, is that when you talk to the practitioners, these are of course people who have only worked on this stupid document for two years or a year. And of course I don't get through it to the extent that they probably do." (EI05: 59) [challenge]

I: "You have now described many networks. If we now offer an additional network on the platform that should not be duplicated, is it more in the interdisciplinary area? In other words, to find new researchers. Earlier you talked about people in the healthcare sector. You wouldn't even know where to find them. It's a kind of researcher Tinder. I find the research partners I need for the next research project. Do you see it more in an area like that or do you really see it in your discipline-

specific area that you just described? (.) It's not supposed to be a duplicate or an additional offer, but it should provide you with added value."

R: "I think that's a danger you quickly run into when you go into it. So if it was to be disciplinary, you would really have to be extremely specific about something. Because otherwise, as I said, there are actually such broad networks. (.) I actually believe that this interdisciplinary thing would be a real added value. That would actually be interesting. And something that doesn't happen that much. As I said, at the moment it's all so clustered, I'd say. It's kind of an open energy community. This is systems analysis and so on. And there's not so much that's a kind of network at the moment. So intermediate discipline." (..)

I: "Would it help you if, for example, different networks from different fields of work were shown on the platform, so that you would know, aha, if I need someone from the social sciences now, I would have to go to network XY and go to the conference?"

R: "That would definitely be interesting, yes." (EI08: 48-51) [service]

"[...] I believe that in these technical disciplines, deep professional networking is much more important than interdisciplinary networking." (EI11: 29) [challenge]

"So the more broadly academic work becomes, the more I think this aspect of networking plays a role, because then the community, i.e. the relevant sub-communities, become so broad, so large, that nobody can claim to know all their colleagues." (EI11: 37) [challenge]

"Perhaps the most likely problem is to familiarize young scientists, who may not come from such strongly networked chairs, with this community and to introduce them to it. That might be the first steps into this community. That is perhaps something that could be consciously supported." (EI11: 39) [challenge]

"It would be helpful to have a platform where you can find aggregated information from experts on the various topics that are relevant in the field, which you can either pass on or use yourself to read up on things that you are not necessarily working on yourself. A fund beyond what Wikipedia offers (...) that would be helpful under certain circumstances. Not scientifically helpful, but for science communication, yes." (EI11: 63-64) [service]

"So what's new for me is this idea that has just popped up as a result of your question, i.e. that you could actually set up a database that is more in the area of science communication in order to be able to respond in areas that are not primarily, i.e. your own research areas." (EI11: 67) [service]

"What is missing or what I would really like to see is stronger networking with technicians, i.e. with people, with engineers, who are actually working in this field with a technical or more technical perspective." (EI14: 10) [challenge]

"So, I'm not yet on a digital platform where you have the feeling that you're talking about something specific or can just throw a general question into the room. So something like Slack for research, energy research would probably be interesting. So really just something moderated, but with the opportunity to engage in a digital exchange." (EI14: 20) [challenge] [service]

I: "You just mentioned a kind of Slack for energy research. What kind of questions would you like to ask there and to whom? And would that perhaps be something like an exchange of best practices with other researchers on methodological issues or how could I imagine something like that?"

R: "Exactly, so basically what I would like to see as questions, for example, actually the topic, who has already collected certain data on various topics? So if, in principle, you also try to network with regard to our project, just as we have now. Who has already collected data on the topic of participation and how did they go about it? So that you can actually exchange information about methods in principle, but also about the existing data more or less. (.) And then, if necessary,

update each other on the current status, where you stand in principle and maybe just get a few pointers here and there." (EI14: 21-22) [challenge] [service]

"One big issue is actually networking. So that's something I would definitely take with me again, especially in the research community, because these contacts that have already been established, or that could certainly be further developed, could really be maintained and intensified." (EI14: 54) [challenge]

"LinkedIn, that's so globally galactic, everyone's there somehow and this one, that's already a pre-sorting by the title alone, well, and I go in with a completely different set of expectations. I really want to connect with people who work in this field, not exactly in my field, but in the energy sector. And I want to find other solar thermal engineers, for example, or perhaps biomass people who work with heat but are looking for something where they can store their heat. So it always has a certain purpose or I approach it with an expectation. In other words, I don't really use LinkedIn at all, because you get flooded with information there. And this is much, much more specific, with a real expectation of networking in a targeted way." (EI16: 63) [challenge] [service]

Need 7: Context information on existing data

"So first of all, of course, I would need information about the circumstances under which this was originally raised. [...] Simply to understand, what was the aim of the research project? How were the interviewees selected? (...) Yes, and then exactly as you say. So a brief contextualization so that I simply know, not in the sense of who exactly is this? But in the thinking of the original project that dealt with this, why were they relevant? So just a short description, it doesn't have to be the person, the actor, the stakeholder, whatever, that would be important in order to be able to continue working with it. And then, of course, the raw data, i.e. the transcript anonymized. It would also be good to know the approximate date of the survey so that you can look things up if they are mentioned in the text. So any legislative initiatives or anything like that that you might not have at hand ad hoc, so that you can look them up to understand what's actually going on." (EI01: 38) [challenge]

"Ultimately, it would be extremely helpful to have a meta-platform that provides you with the sub-sources for all relevant points. In some cases, it is actually helpful if you then have secondary data, especially in the literature. (.) You usually have a lot of trouble finding out if I find a value in the literature, but it doesn't fit, then finding out the primary source. That is actually helpful. I think it would really help to have a kind of automatic chaining of metadata etc., so to speak. Because it's often helpful to get the data in the most detailed form that you can. Because then you can always aggregate and process it yourself. That's always relatively easy. It's difficult when other people have already touched the data and have somehow processed it themselves. Because then it's difficult to process them again, so to speak. (.) In other words, it would be great to have the opportunity to access primary data in some way. (.) And then, of course, it would be ideal to always know for each data set which assumptions have somehow been included in the calculation, i.e. if it is not primary data." (EI08: 29) [challenge]

I: "Would you say that it is generally a challenge to know what assumptions have been made because they are not transparent?"

R: "Yes, that is definitely a big problem. So that's a problem above all with many of the large studies, etc. I would say that there is now a very large open source community and open modeling community that also works very transparently. But especially when we still look at some EU Commission scenarios or something like that, which were made with primes, that's just a black box. And at the end of the day, you see the results and you might see some input data, but you don't actually know everything that happens in between. And that is definitely still a big challenge."

I: "To go back to that and why is it important for you to know exactly what assumptions are being made? (..)"

R: "Yes, good, so that you can understand it and possibly process the data further in a meaningful way. Because the problem is that I run the risk of my data simply getting worse and worse in quality the more often it is somehow put through the wolf again and reassembled. Because if I have primary data that I can somehow aggregate myself, then I can tailor it to my own sectors etc. and then it's right, then it's somehow based, founded on the data." (EI08: 34-37) [challenge]

"Then you have your process flow chart, your process steps, then you pop in the [database], then you say it's an electricity mix from Germany and not from Europe, that looks different again or whatever, it's a mishmash of everything and you get a different result every time. Cotton, organic cotton, is a glaring example. You think, great, it must have a huge positive impact if I use that as opposed to normal cotton." (EI09: 31) [challenge]

R: "And I look at that. I look at where the data comes from and why is it like that? But if I now take the, I simply say, okay, my cotton now comes from the USA, it looks good again.(.) And that has nothing to do with reality to some extent. And [name] is currently holding a disputation."

I: "Exactly, I know [institution]."

R: "Yes, he did that too and we found out, we have taken apart a data center. (.) [Name] was also involved and wanted to replicate this in the life cycle assessment. And [name] uses this [database] and saw that this is standard electronic waste. So it's not computer waste, but a hairdryer, a toaster and all sorts of things. Exactly, and that's a mix and we should use this mix for our data centers. And then we said, no, that's not possible." (EI09: 33-35) [challenge]

R1: "Well, if a platform somehow aggregated the input data that is important to me, that would be really helpful."

R2: "Especially if, similar to what we tried to do with the [platform], it actually provides the processes behind this data generation, makes them transparent, uses some kind of scripts, Jupyter, Dotbox or whatever. I would find it very helpful if they could provide this directly, so that in case of doubt you can understand how the data is generated and reproduce or adapt it if necessary. I could also imagine that it would be really interesting, particularly with regard to relevant scenario calculations, if the underlying input data from, let's say, at least large and important energy system analyses or scenarios were actually available in some kind of structural form - I would find that very helpful." (EI10: 78-79) [challenge] [service]

"So on the one hand, you want to represent the data within its uncertainty using models. On the other hand, you don't want to overfit. And for this, the assessment of the uncertainty is essential. And this is not as well documented as the data itself. This means that you have to go back to the original articles for each individual data set." (EI11: 23) [challenge]

"This total uncertainty for each individual measuring point should also be specified in tables. However, this is typically not included in the databases; instead, the databases often only contain the measurement point itself." (EI11: 25) [challenge]

I: "Are there any other best practices that you share in addition to the data and measurement standards?" (14 second pause)

R: "Well, of course, if you are now at the modeling level, then best practice is also about how to evaluate such models. So if we publish a model, if we publish an equation of state, then it is essential to compare it with the measurement data that was used for the adjustment or comparison. In other words, these are simply deviation diagrams where you can see that the deviations from some data set are not just on average, but are as large point by point. And then criteria that are more general also play a role. So where it has become established (.) to always show certain state variables, certain progressions of state equations, because you know that these are criteria for good extrapolability, for numerical stability. (.) Standards have been established to which the deeply involved groups adhere, orient themselves and with which such publications of models, of equations of state, can be better evaluated by experts." (EI11: 32-33) [challenge] [service]

"We work a lot with measurement data, i.e. linear measurement data. (..) And we look at this measurement data ourselves. In other words, we first have to get a geographical reference point so that we know where this measurement data comes from. And then it's measurement data from the depths. So we look at this data and always need a measurement report or what is known as a header. The file also states what was measured when, where and how. So that's a description of the measurement. And then we look at the data and can sort out any incorrect data. If somehow a measurement did not work in a certain depth interval, we sort it out and of course document it. That is one aspect of quality management for us. The other thing is that when the measurement data comes in, the temperature was measured, especially at these underground temperatures. But this is not the true temperature of the subsurface, because drilling was carried out, i.e. the drilling was carried out technically. And when drilling, a liquid is put into the borehole to keep it cool and stable. This means that the temperature from this borehole is too cold and we have to correct the temperatures. We then develop temperature correction methods, which we then publish. And for us, this also means quality management, so we don't just put in the raw data, but we say that the data has been changed for technical reasons and we correct it using a scientific process so that it is as close as possible to the true underground temperature." (EI16: 39) [challenge] [service]

Need 8: Reputation for shared data sets

I: "This extra effort that you have to put into processing the data. Would there be any other incentives for you that would encourage you to take on this extra work yourself, instead of it perhaps being dictated by the project?"

R: "Hm. Yes, of course. Ideally, it's definitely a great thing. Of course it is. Yes. (...) It's just science. So much of science is unpaid anyway. I could imagine, so of course it's a form of mention, of course it's not bad in the sense that you might be mentioned in a publication. So being an author is unrealistic if you've only processed the data, because the authors have done everything else. I would also find that unfair, actually. But it would be cool to be mentioned." (EI01: 39-41) [service]

"And knowledge in all honor, but I think I would be more motivated to do it if I had the concrete prospect that someone else could really do something with it. So that would be even cooler if you knew you weren't working for the forest. In the sense of, let's see, maybe in ten years, take a look at it or something, but to know, hey or somehow, if I could use it in my own teaching or for students who are writing theses or something" (EI01: 43) [service]

I: "You said that there might also be the option of setting up licenses that state, Hey, if you want to work with my data set, then I have to be listed as a co-author on your paper. You just said you think that's unfair. Can you explain again why you don't think that would be justified?"

R: "I just think it depends on the paper. If the paper follows my research question and then perhaps deals with a different nuance, then I think it's fair to be on it, because then it was somehow my idea. If my data is used to work on something completely different and the whole theoretical work is something completely different from what I do, the whole contextualization is completely different, then I think my data is just a means to an end. A very important means to an end. But then I find that I haven't done any idealistic work, as far as the structure of the paper is concerned. I didn't co-write it, so I think it somehow depends on how close the researchers or authors are to my research with their research question and with their classification, with their derivation of relevance. But if they do something completely unique with it, which is certainly possible with very explorative data. I do have a tendency towards very narrative interviews, always rather involuntarily, but accordingly I would just say, no, I would want to have acknowledged that the data is being used. But then I don't necessarily have to stand on it. Besides, maybe I'm not even behind what they write. I often have the problem that I'm on it somewhere because I wrote on it. It's a bit uncomfortable for me, to be honest." (EI01: 50-53) [challenge] [service]

"There are methods in other areas that allow you to upload data sets, even with citation and so on, which is better than nothing. Of course, it only counts like this, depending on where you need something, but it's not in proportion to the effort behind it" (EI02: 85) [challenge] [service]

"Quite often, I think, you also have the feeling that, well, okay, you don't know how many users would really want to use it. If I now knew more specifically, okay, the 30 municipal utilities would use the tool or the information as soon as I uploaded it, I would perhaps do it sooner, because we also have an intrinsic motivation or could then also advertise by being able to explicitly say, I know that 30 other project partners have also implemented it afterwards. Or if I know how much it will bring, if I can estimate how much it will bring later." (EI02: 87) [service]

"Another argument is, [name], you can still build up your reputation if you provide your data and people then work with it and cite it. That will also increase the citations of your papers, where I then say, yes, that's actually true. So you're actually right. Yes, and I realize that now we're already doing research where we used to keep the data and now we say, hey, we can process the data set this way and that way, then as many people as possible will cite the paper." (EI04: 33) [service]

I: "Well, you don't get anything for uploading it for others out of kindness. So others might be happy because they think, hey, that's really cool data and interviews, but you as a researcher don't get anything out of it personally. If you think about it from this perspective, would you still want to do it?"

R: "Hm, it depends a bit and I think it also depends a bit on what the project has to do with. It depends a bit on the fact that I know, will the pages, how likely is it that people will come across this data at all?" (EI05: 31-32) [service]

I: "What added value would there have to be for you to upload them to another platform? Or an incentive?" (...)

R: "An incentive. It would definitely have to be easy to use. That would be the most important thing, I think. It would have to be easy to use. As soon as it's easy to use, it's no great effort. As long as the effort is low, it's not a problem anyway. If the effort isn't low, then it depends on whether I, as the person uploading, feel that it's worth it. Especially if I have the feeling that there's a strong community behind it, that I'm not uploading it in a vacuum, but that people will interact with it. That's one of the things with Zenodo and so on. Zenodo is extremely cool. It's extremely simple. That's exactly why I use it. It's super simple. You can just upload any format you want. You get a DOI. Mega good. [...] You never get any feedback on your Zenodo data sets. No one has ever said, I've looked at it and what's the value, or I have a different opinion on something. It would be cool if you uploaded things, if there was some kind of interaction, if you had the feeling that there was a platform where there were people who were interested in the data, I had to look at it and discuss it." (EI8: 68-69) [service]

I: "What motivated you to make them available to the public?"

R: "Because we were just as much in the dark as everyone else. And when you say that we were publicly funded. Why should we withhold these figures now? I have no added value at all. Except that I can say that I haven't edge-patched the data after all. That's such a sandbox gift. That's my scoop, your scoop. (.) So we never asked ourselves that question."

I: "But you didn't get a reward for uploading it, did you?" //R: "Nope." (..) //

R: "I think somewhere in the datasets it says that they are from our research project, but then it says the research project and not the name. (...) Yes, it would be nice to leave your footprints." (EI09: 42-45) [challenge] [service]

"And that doesn't immediately result in co-authorship, but it does provide a source citation option, which is great for many people when they see, oh, I've created a dataset here and it's being used so often, then it seems to be an important dataset." (EI16: 55) [service]

Need 9: Time-saving and uncomplicated data processing

"It's kind of tricky, because the upload itself is quick, but processing it in such a way that you can show it to people is even more difficult. And then processing it so that people can use it in a

meaningful way is even more difficult, because then I need to annotate the text and create a manual. And so on and so forth. We or the modelers do this because they have an increased interest in people using their things and they should use their model and so on. And you need a manual for that, otherwise nobody will use it." (EI02: 85) [challenge]

"But to be fair, you always write it in two sentences and then it falls to the back because it's at the end. And that's the last thing you can't quite manage. That's why it's not so easy. And with certain datasets, it's not enough to upload them once, you also have to do a certain amount of maintenance on the website or the domain or something, which also costs capacity in the long term." (EI02: 87) [challenge]

I: "And how high would that be? So it sounds a bit as if the probability that you would do this at all would be rather low in a normal research day and your capacities. Or am I interpreting that wrong?"

R: "Well, that's just because, let's put it this way, there are now quite a lot of artificial intelligence tools that do the transcribing for you, that completely transcribe all the language for you and understand it very well. And then? That means you don't have this super elaborate dot dot dot, pause, swallow. But of course you already have the content somehow. And if you actually go in from an expert interview perspective and not from a narrative perspective, then that's actually enough, in my opinion. And if it's that easy, then I'll do it, then I'd do it." (EI05: 29-30) [service]

"It is important for other scientists who would use this dataset that a description is provided at the same time, because the columns within a dataset are not necessarily always self-explanatory.(.) That it is transparent what exactly is contained in this column and how the information contained there was prepared." (EI06&07: 101) [challenge]

"And if you write a paper yourself, then you know how your scripts work. You don't pay much attention to the documentation of the whole thing. And when it comes to data preparation, you might not always be completely clean. So not clean in the documentation.(...) For this coding review, it was a huge effort to put it into a form that others could understand, which is always a process in the research process, this data preparation and so on. (...) Accordingly, you might have an overview yourself if you, even if I were to make this data set available to others, it probably wouldn't be used because no one could get through it. In other words, another point that could perhaps be interesting is always when I make a conscious decision to do so, and ultimately it is a conscious decision to make data public, (.) actually it's only useful if the whole thing is reasonably well documented and the data set is clean and tidy. But at the same time, this means extra work for me, which may not bring me any direct added value." (EI06&07: 116) [challenge]

"But the amount of work involved is definitely a point. I had once considered publishing with Data in Brief and the journal, for example, also requires sufficient documentation to be published. And the amount of work involved was too much for me in that case. So I had a raw data set that was also easy to understand in principle, but it wasn't possible to publish it because of the extra work involved in documentation and that's exactly why it didn't happen." (EI06&07: 128) [challenge]

"But what takes a lot of time and effort is, of course, developing these scripts that transform the data. So, of course, that was an initial time expenditure and you also have to keep it up to date. In other words, it's a certain amount of work." (EI08: 61) [challenge]

I: "What would make it easier to create transcripts? So is it possible to make them available automatically or is it very case-specific? (...) If we now want to offer a service on the platform that helps with this transcript creation, which you just described as a challenge. So what would that be?" (..)

R: "I think it would be interesting to see if there are any approaches to providing something like that. Of course, I think that's also specific to the model relationship, because we always need a translation from what it's called in our model to what it's called in the platform and what the data format is, etc. (...) In other words, nobody will really be able to do this translation work for you.

What you can do in any case is to provide examples of existing scripts, some of which you can then perhaps adapt for your own purposes. I don't know if you can make it generic to the extent that people can simply use it directly. I don't know that. It would certainly be interesting, yes, definitely. And above all, there are a few established data formats that exist. So there's the OEP format, there's the IMC data format. (.) There is some kind of data format from the Spine people. If you had at least some standard conversions between these data formats, that would actually be pretty cool." (EI08: 62-63) [service]

I: "What added value would there have to be for you to upload them to another platform? Or an incentive?" (...)

R: "An incentive. It would definitely have to be easy to use. That would be the most important thing, I think. It would have to be easy to use. As soon as it's easy to use, it's no great effort. As long as the effort is low, it's not a problem anyway. If the effort isn't low, then it depends on whether I, as the person uploading, feel that it's worth it. Especially if I have the feeling that there's a strong community behind it, that I'm not uploading it in a vacuum, but that people will interact with it. That's one of the things with Zenodo and so on. Zenodo is extremely cool. It's extremely simple. That's exactly why I use it. It's super simple. You can just upload any format you want. You get a DOI. Mega good" (EI8: 68-69) [service]

I: "Is it the case in your department that data sets that you make available to others are cited? (.)

R: "Only the data sets? I don't think so." (.)

I: "Would that be an extra incentive for you if it were cited? If your data were used elsewhere, that you might put more time into processing it?" (.)

R: "That would definitely be an incentive."

I: "Or don't you see that as a central point?" (....)

R: "It is interesting. It's certainly not a bad thing. (...) The idea of this platform is that ideally there should be a community behind it, that people should validate and exchange their data together in order to avoid duplication of work and to fundamentally improve data quality. Of course, this would also include mutual referencing." (EI08: 70-75) [service]

I: "This data set, the [name] there, (..) it probably had to be processed for this platform, because you couldn't just, can you quantify roughly how much work it was to get it ready, so to speak, camera ready?"

R: "Wow, I think it's like writing a paper, isn't it? A paper is written so quickly, but then you have to polish it and read the review again. Like 80-20? Yes, so at least a quarter, three quarters." (EI09: 54-55) [challenge]

"So, giving data, or if we now have companies that say, yes, you can do something with our data, (.) put that in. But how do you put it in there so that it's also useful for others? I think that's still a lot of work." (EI09: 55) [challenge]

"First of all, the disclosure of code and data, although to be honest, disclosure is relatively easy in itself. I can quickly dump all the files into the Zenodo repository.(.) And people can't do much with that. So going from basically traceable or reproducible to actually simple and usable with low access barriers is a huge step." (EI10: 54) [challenge]

"That's another challenge, of course, to process this data accordingly, as you said earlier, and make it usable." (EI14: 42) [challenge]

"We are in a somewhat advantageous position in terms of geodata, because there are geological state offices and a data format is specified, including a European data format. Of course, the geological services are still far from having everything in this data format. It's called Inspire, this data format for geodata and also for metadata in the geosciences, the Inspire format for surface data and Borehole-ML is what it's called, an ML, a meta-language. (.) This language, or this data format, is now also where all borehole data has to go. Of course, we also do this ourselves. We take this data format, we use it. (.) But, as I said, it is already predefined because there are these

geological state offices and state geological services. In this respect, we no longer have to worry about any new format, but rather have to make sure that our data is transferred into this format." (EI16:45) [service]

Need 10: Increase usability of existing data

"Converting always takes more time than you would have liked and nobody really wants to do it. But it's still always incredibly important and you're always missing data points, whether it's not resolved enough in terms of time, whether it's somehow spatially, then it's just the EU with or without Switzerland, Norway or Turkey, or is Russia included or not? So that's their understanding. What is that? Are they all the same? Are all technologies included or not? So that means something is still missing. It's always not quite in the perfect format somehow and something can always go wrong with units or whatever." (EI02: 70) [challenge]

I: "What does data availability mean? So does it mean CSV, i.e. tables, data in a certain format, in some source, platform or is it simply on the Internet, unstructured information?" (..)

R: "That's just, exactly, that's often the case. This is information. The information is theoretically freely accessible, but of course it's not processed, for example via social media or something like that. There are various data streams that can theoretically be used to obtain information, but in order to ultimately evaluate it scientifically, you first have to put it into a format in order to be able to carry out this evaluation." (EI06&07: 53-54) [challenge]

"Most of the time, or at least in my experience, the most exciting results are only obtained when you link several different pieces of data together. In other words, maybe for this platform that you want to offer, one added value would be to offer this data at all, the other added value would be to suggest the whole thing, or if that is somehow possible, to suggest links between this data. If you think of relational databases, then you have table A, table B and they can be linked to each other via some key relationship." (EI06&07: 56) [service]

"As I have just described, other things, such as demand data, are just completely mixed up. So you can find them in some databases, but in the rarest cases you can use them directly. So that really is the problem. So we find, for example, now IEA, there is also World Country Data or something, there we find electricity production in every country or something. That's not a problem. We get that broken down by energy source. That's great. That would also be something we need in theory. But the problem is that we can't use it directly. So we always have to transform the data in some way, because the problem is that we then have to differentiate between what is quasi exogenous electricity demand, which we don't represent in the model, and what is endogenous. And then calculating around this is almost impossible to automate and requires a relatively long calibration process later on. (...) So I don't know of any database that exists where we can simply do this now. I also don't know if that's possible, to be honest. Because I think it's really a big challenge that every model has different coverage. Each model somehow covers different sectors, (...) different technologies, and so I don't know if it's super easy to harmonize." (EI08: 27) [challenge]

R: "I think that's because we just have a problem, so we don't have a, here's a database and do something with it. Instead, we have to somehow work everything out on foot. [...] Because it's not, do Matlab and then take database XYZ."

I: "Exactly, take the CSV out and enter."

R: "Exactly. We work a lot with CSV data, but we usually get it from the industry and then have to process it for ourselves." (EI09: 63-65) [challenge]

"And above all, they are available in forms that are not directly machine-readable. In Germany, for example, we had an example of renewable generation data that was provided by the four grid operators in different file formats, in different formats, rows and columns and in individual sheets and files. But not even uniformly. [...] In other words, there is a lot available, but the data is not directly usable. And then it's an incredible amount of duplicated work if everyone prepares this primary data themselves. And then there are all these, I haven't even said it yet, so of course there

are also errors. Missing data, any scaling that you actually have to do if not everything is reported, etc. There are a thousand things that everyone has to sort out in a decentralized way. And of course, it would be much more efficient if all of this could be cleaned up in a comprehensible way." (EI10: 60) [challenge]

"The climate data are very good, so okay, they are very good. They are accessible. The pre-processing is a hassle and it's really exhausting." (EI12: 15) [challenge]

"That would probably be this second wish, to have the data already usable in such a way that it is relatively easy to work with it." (EI14: 42) [challenge]

"And can also access this data and generate statistics. So it's like an interactive web tool and everyone can link the data as they need it." (EI16: 41) [service]

Need 11: Comprehensive knowledge about data management

"To be honest, up to now we have simply stored the qualitative things in our office, relatively unsorted according to the individual research projects in the folders, so that as long as we know what was done in the research project and which papers are there, we can find the things again. So they are stored digitally. This means that handwritten notes were usually not really sorted, but they were usually scanned or typed in at some point during the paper writing process" (EI02: 72) [challenge]

"I do a lot of qualitative research, which is of course very time-consuming. So we're doing an interview right now. I don't think it's a secret that when you prepare interviews like this, you do them, conduct them and evaluate them. Of course, you always have to generate a lot of data, including where to store what, how to secure it and how to save it. And then you always need content from each interviewee. Then they don't answer straight away. You have to remind them again. So, of course, there are a lot of processes that are very time-consuming, and I don't know if you've done it a few times, but you know you have to plan the appropriate time. Maybe there are ways to optimize it somehow. Or maybe to help others who are just starting out. So, templates. How do you deal with something like that? Always lists, how do you keep good lists with you when you are not just working on a document alone?" (EI03: 21) [challenge] [service]

"So I've just checked that you need a metadata record and a metadata schema for each data record." (EI04: 37) [challenge]

I: "Our interviews have given us the impression that there is still a need among many researchers to continue their education in order to address precisely these kinds of questions: Where can I store my data so that it can be found? What steps do I actually have to take? For example, if I want to publish a data set? That is not so easy, for example if you still have to fill out metadata schemas, etc. Would you say that you still have a need for further education in this area? And if so, what would you like? Would it be something like compulsory training courses through the department or something that you can inform yourself on a website and simply pick out the information you need."

R: "(..) I think that would be good. And a closed course like that. So if you then, because it is actually something that you would not otherwise come into contact with in your studies" (EI05: 40-41) [service]

"And if you write a paper yourself, then you know how your scripts work. You don't pay much attention to the documentation of the whole thing. And when it comes to data processing, you might not always be very clean. So not clean in the documentation. (...) For this coding review, it was a huge effort to put it into a form that others could understand, which is always a process in the research process, this data processing and so on. (...) Accordingly, you yourself might have an overview if you, even if I were to make this data set available to others, it probably wouldn't be used because no one can get through it. In other words, another point that could perhaps be interesting is always when I make a conscious decision to do so, and ultimately it is a conscious decision to make data public, (.) actually it's only useful if the whole thing is reasonably well documented and the data set is clean and tidy. But at the same time, this means extra work for me, which may not bring me any direct added value." (EI06&07: 116) [challenge]

I: "If we think about how we can use the platform to help researchers who have little experience with it, do you have any ideas? You said you benefited from the experience. (.) If you don't have the opportunity to exchange ideas, what formats could there be? Is it a template for what a data management plan could look like? Is it an explanatory video or what form could it take?" (.)

R: "I'm basically a pretty big fan of video tutorials and so on. I think it would be important to just provide basic information about what already exists. (.) I think there are a lot of things that already exist and that you can use. (.) I'm actually a big fan of videos and really making sure that the databases that exist and the file formats that exist and so on are documented and described well enough to make them usable for people. (.) Because if that is the case, then I would say (.) a very large part of the work has already been done, because you can actually access an extremely large number of good resources." (EI08: 56-57) [service]

I: "And what kind of training would help you there? It could also be a service that could be on a platform, in the form of a template showing how such a plan can be structured, a best practice video or what would you like? Let's assume you have found a great project tender that you really want to apply for with your team. But it says that you have to submit a data management plan."

R: "So what now? Yes, then maybe a how-to explainer example would be for the field here, energy system analysis, a few examples or a little guideline on what you have to do. That would definitely be very useful." (.) (EI10: 67-68) [service]

"So I think I know shockingly little about how to really clean it now. Yes, I've always treated it very, very neglected, I would say, with, yes, you can take care of it when you have time. I think I've always learned the most in situations where you realize that something has gone wrong because you somehow didn't save the data set you used in the way you used it and suddenly completely different results come out that were then somehow clear, You definitely need the data to be somewhere in the format in which you want it to be, so either it has to be very clear which pre-processing steps I used and the script also has to be somewhere, or the data after the script has run should also be somewhere. Yes, but it's also a bit of a somewhere because you move from university to university in your academic career and somehow migrate things back and forth and they're not there now, yes. So there are a lot of courses here, but I haven't attended any of them." (EI12: 39) [challenge]

"So the one thing is, exactly, I have handled my own research data so badly that I had some intermediate step of data that I simply couldn't go back to. It was completely unclear to me how I got from the initial data to this intermediate step, how I ended up there, and I simply couldn't use it anymore, simply because the process wasn't properly documented." (EI12: 59) [challenge]

I: "In the preliminary questionnaire, you described the need for research data management as rather high, if I'm reading this correctly. I'm seeing very high here. Have you ever had to create a data management plan, perhaps for a project proposal? That would be my question. And what kind of service would you want in order to cover the demand that you have described as high?" (..)

R: "Well, I think that, in principle, basic, fundamental knowledge would be necessary. In fact, we actually created a data management plan as part of the [organization]-project, i.e. as part of the [organization]-project. (...) But that ticked these general boxes, in quotation marks. So how is the data collected, exactly, on the one hand, how is the data collected, how is the data then analyzed and how is the data stored? And I have the feeling that a bit of basic knowledge might actually be necessary. What does a data management plan look like? What would be good scientific practice in order to really put the whole thing on a solid footing, not on a solid footing, but on a solid footing?" (14: 29-30) [challenge] [service]

I: "How do you estimate the extra effort required to prepare the data accordingly and add additional information, as you have just described? And what kind of incentive would you have to have to do something like that? So when would you say, yes, in that case I'll definitely do it and invest the extra time?" (..)

R: "Well, I think it would probably make sense to approach data collection from the outset with the appropriate glasses or with the appropriate standard, to put it that way. That means that if you

had a certain guideline to say that if you prepare your data in this or that way, then, or collect it, then you could ensure that this data can be used in the long term. So I think this very first step would be necessary." (EI14: 37-38) [service]

Need 12: Comprehensive knowledge about legal aspects for sharing data

"I've also had the situation myself where someone would have liked to work with data that I once collected, but that would have been difficult under data protection law, because you actually have to know that at the time the data is collected and then you have to obtain consent for it to be passed on, even if only in anonymized form. And I didn't do that at the time. And exactly with the person from whom I would have liked to have the data or where it would have been cool to be able to use it, which was also the case that it was simply legally impossible." (EI01: 26) [challenge]

"Well, I think that in order to be able to do anything with it, I still have to have an idea despite the anonymization. Who is the person who is somehow providing information about some topic? Not in the sense that it's Heinz Müller, 61, from the Odenwald, but just an opponent of wind energy who has been involved since then and then perhaps, depending on how I provide data, it can also be helpful to mark. Okay, they belong to the same protest initiative or are from the same region, depending on the case. So in this example, I think that's important, and the trick is to make it so diffuse that it's not possible to clearly identify the person unless they've agreed to it, but at the same time to make it so precise that someone else can do something with it. I know it, but I can also look it up. And I am also allowed to look it up, because I have permission to work with it. Exactly. And another problem, of course, is that the GDPR also allows you to withdraw this consent if it is then stored in another database. And this transfer may only take place after the end of the project and then I have other contact persons. Um, then the interviewees must also be aware that they can still say too theoretically. So it's very unlikely, I think, it's very rare that someone says after three and a half years I want to have the data deleted. Yes, but there has to be someone there who you can contact, who can reliably assign it, who can reliably delete it. And it's a challenge to know this infrastructure well enough in advance to be able to obtain consent." (EI01: 36) [challenge]

"In the qualitative area (...) we don't usually disclose our things because it's much more difficult for data protection reasons" (EI02: 70) [challenge]

"But, as I said, there is also the question of data protection, so that it is somehow compliant. And we have people sign all their requests when they give an interview. And it doesn't say that we'll upload the complete transcript openly, because perhaps no one would agree to that, because it would then be possible to trace who it is. At some point, if I put up the complete text and then code it, depending on how clean I get, it's also too detailed. And if I then abstract it so much that it no longer works. Then it doesn't help anyone else either." (EI02: 120) [challenge]

"You always have to look at how you can really ensure that it is not possible to identify who said what, not naming companies and the like." (EI03: 25) [challenge]

R: "But interview results, so really any raw data or anything like that, I don't give that out now either, but really only summarized results. Yes."

I: "So you haven't published transcripts or anything like that yet."

R: "No, that would, that's not possible, that's really not possible. So from my point of view, also for data protection reasons. I believe that. If you were to do that. No, I believe that. So, yes, I think that's really too individual. And then it actually is. Yes, well, I think it's too easy to really understand which person it was. Depending on, because sometimes you really do ask very precisely which project it is? And that really is very specific information, some of it is very sensitive data. I have now also conducted many surveys or interviews where the focus was really on specific energy infrastructure projects. What is going well, what is not? What are the challenges of stakeholder participation? And I actually wanted to get more best practices and more information

from the stakeholders or interview partners. But then it wouldn't be called a project. Wouldn't we like that to become somehow prominent, that there's something wrong with it? So of course it is sometimes very sensitive, especially when projects or processes are still running, to talk about them openly. So, of course, it's not just that the interviewee should be protected, but of course it's always about entire companies or a society that is ultimately affected, or we're really always talking about being affected by a certain project or intervention." (EI03: 25-27) [challenge]

"But of course, I mean, you always have to be careful with certain things. When can you share what and how? Especially when it's sometimes doctoral students. You always have to be a bit more careful, of course, because you'll be the first to publish it." (EI03: 64) [challenge]

"If I had to conduct interviews, I have to be honest and say that I don't know enough about how to actually conduct interviews. I'm actually a big fan of them because interviews can actually give you a really nice in-depth perspective. But I actually know, so if I, let's say, let's take this hypothetical example further and I would say I had conducted these interviews and I knew what the data protection regulations were and I knew how to anonymize something like this appropriately." (EI05: 28) [challenge]

I: "Would there be anything against making the data records that you have just discussed publicly available?"

R: "In my case, I'm not so sure, because that could be problematic in terms of data protection law. But I don't know exactly. (...) At least we actually had problems with a project proposal that we wrote, because we have this data and may not necessarily be allowed to use it or make it publicly available, at least in the granularity that we have. Because ultimately, if you really wanted to, you could draw conclusions about individual people." (EI06&07: 94-95) [challenge]

"And perhaps one last point, these data records that we then generate, we also combine them with data from various other sources, which we may also request, where we have to say exactly, for this and this use, I need the data, then I get the data. And then, with our data, our data set is created, to what extent we are authorized to use this data, even if the raw data or the data that we have received from other sources, even in aggregated form or something like that, has been processed in there, whether we are authorized. So there are also legal issues where you tend to say, I'd rather not give out the data, not that there are any problems with a third party who has provided me with parts of the data." (EI06&07: 109) [challenge]

I: "Do you have needs in the form of, I'll call them courses in the field of research data management and if so, where, for example, do you feel that you are not yet really well covered? I have heard that the legal framework is such an issue. How do you see that?" (...)

R: "Yes, that's the reason why I ticked the checkbox medium, because I have a lot of unanswered questions about legal certainty. (...) Exactly. As far as the processing, storage, visualization and evaluation of the data is concerned, I would say very high. So medium, because legal uncertainty." (EI06&07: 129-130) [challenge]

Need 13: Ensured quality management for uploaded data

"And then, yes, admin, if there was someone who responded to questions, comments or suggestions, so if someone said there seemed to be something inconsistent in the data, if they then responded to it, perhaps they would do it in such a way that it was also visible to others, (.) that would of course be helpful too. That would give me the feeling that it was quality-controlled." (EI10: 87) [challenge] [service]

"We don't just put all the data in there, otherwise you have good and bad data and incorrect data. In other words, that's where our geoscientific work comes in, that we do quality management. For me, that is the most, most, most important thing. And if this is a freely accessible information system, then we also make sure that no data is lost, that it is versioned, that the versioning is recognized. And that it contains both raw data and interpreted data. And the interpreted data in

particular has to be versioned. And with the raw data, you have to sort out measurement errors so that no one, who perhaps doesn't have the insight, suddenly models with a measurement error afterwards." (E116:37) [challenge]

"What we also have is that we have different data categories. Firstly, according to the age of the data, then uncertainties that can arise during measurement. So we have very reliable data, less reliable data and uncertain data. So we also have different data categories. And then it is important for the scientists to be able to treat the different data differently when weighting. So the data with the lowest uncertainty has a very high weighting in models and the data with a low, i.e. high, uncertainty has a low weighting. And we communicate that and document it." (E116: 39) [service]

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